

A coupled OpenMC and OpenFOAM analysis method applied to heat pipes micro reactors for space applications

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ABSTRACT

In support of micro-reactor design, Monte Carlo neutronics solvers and finite-volume thermal codes are employed to accurately capture, respectively, the power deposition and temperature distribution within the core. A major challenge lies in coupling the locally accurate stochastic Monte Carlo power field with the smooth, cell-resolved input required by thermal solvers. In this work, developed within the SELENE project framework, a one-way coupled neutronic-thermal analysis for the Surface Nuclear Reactor (SNR) core design is presented. Neutronics and thermal simulations are performed using OpenMC and OpenFOAM, respectively, while the MEDCoupling library is employed to manipulate, map and interpolate numerical fields between the two codes. The methodology, based on hexahedral meshes generated with the in-house hexaBundleMesher tool, aims at ensuring accurate transfer of power deposition data and preservation of the underlying physical distributions. The effectiveness of the coupling strategy and the reliability of the resulting thermal predictions are assessed for a preliminary SNR core configuration.

Keywords: OpenMC, OpenFOAM, Numerical Code Coupling, Space Nuclear Reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear micro reactors for space applications are designed to be compact systems to better handle their transport into space. Instead of a typical core configuration, where a coolant fluid flows through the core to cool the fuel elements, heat pipes can be used for cooling the reactor core: they are devices using two phase flows to remove the heat from the core. The global coolant system is then composed by a set of heat pipes that are usually arranged into a regular lattice. Each heat pipe is independent from the others and is a completely passive cooling device, thus improving the intrinsic safety level of the nuclear system. This type of reactors, to tackle the compactness challenge, have typically complex geometrical arrangements best modeled, from the neutronic side, by MonteCarlo codes. Similarly, from the thermal side, finite element or volume codes are the most suitable option to reliably simulate the temperature field in the various core regions. The main challenge of the above types of codes is coupling a locally accurate stochastic solution of the power deposition field coming from MonteCarlo codes with the need for a smooth power density distribution input to thermal solvers. Various works have tried to address this challenge such as [1, 2, 3].

In the present paper, a methodology for a one-way coupled neutronic and thermal analysis, using the OpenMC MonteCarlo code and the OpenFOAM Computational Fluid Dynamic code, is described and applied to a case study evolved from the preliminary fuel assembly design developed for the SELENE project [4]. With this setup, the thermal power distribution that is computed by OpenMC is used in OpenFOAM as a source term for the energy balance equation. At the current state, no temperature feedback is used in the neutronic calculations, but it will be considered in future developments of the methodology.

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Figure 1. Sketch of the coupling algorithm steps from mesh generation to thermal analysis.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 the case study is introduced. In Section 3 the methodology is discussed, together with a description of the used codes and of the coupling strategy. Finally, in Section 4 and 5 the obtained results are presented and the conclusions of the present work are withdrawn.

2. CASE STUDY

For practically showcasing the methodology application an *ad hoc* configuration was constructed based on the Fuel Assembly (FA) concept presented in [4], along with the requirements and assessments that lead to the actual configuration. The FA consists of an hexagonal block of fuel material containing five pins of moderator and two Sodium Heat Pipes (HP) arranged into a regular hexagonal lattice. As reported in [4], TRISO fuel was selected, featuring a UO_2 kernel with an enrichment smaller than 20 wt.% (HALEU). Solid moderators have been identified as the most suitable option, more specifically metal hydrides based on Zirconium as first choice.

In the case study used in this work, a fictitious core configuration is created and composed of 55 FA in a pseudo-cylindrical shape. The number of FAs has been selected based on the HP design power [4] and following the volume and mass constraints of extra-terrestrial transport:

- axially the FA assembly — excluding the reflector — has a height roughly less than one meter;
- radially FAs are arranged to stay well within one meter of diameter.

For simplicity, and without altering the showcasing of the methodology, no reflector is considered.

For a nuclear system, the coupled neutronic and thermal analyses support the design phase, however thermal feedback for the neutronic calculations, namely thermal expansion of the geometry and the temperature dependence of cross sections, is beyond the scope of this paper and only a one-way coupling strategy is presented. Nevertheless, fully coupled calculations will be exploited in future developments of the presented methodology.

3. METHODOLOGY

In the present Section we describe the methodology that has been used to build a numerical code coupling procedure between the `OpenMC` and `OpenFOAM` codes for the neutronic and thermal analyses of a reactor core. The code coupling procedure is needed to transfer the `OpenMC` computed thermal source distribution, in the reactor core, to `OpenFOAM`. As shown in Figure 1, the sequence of operations starts with the generation of the meshes for `OpenMC` and the thermal codes: the first is used as reference for sampling and storing the `OpenMC` solution, while the latter is used as computational grid for solving the thermal field in the reactor core. In the following, each of the analysis steps, namely neutronic analysis,

Figure 2. Core Unstructured Mesh cross sectional views

code coupling and thermal analysis, is discussed in detail.

3.1. Neutronic analysis using OpenMC

The simulations were conducted using OpenMC in the 0.15.0 version with ENDF/B-VIII.0 as nuclear data library. The creation of the core model presented challenges in accurately reproducing the configuration, as a detailed representation of TRISO particles is inherently difficult. Representing multilayered micrometric spheres randomly located is not computationally feasible in OpenMC due to the complexity of the core configuration. To overcome this issue, the fuel region was modeled as a single mixture material via volume homogenization. The approximation introduced by this simulation choice was evaluated by previous investigations in terms of the multiplication constant, as shown in [4]. In terms of power distribution, the uniform dispersion of fuel throughout the volume leads to the loss of the physical detail that, in reality, power generation occurs mainly within the kernel. However, this information has little impact on the distribution result when considering the high density of TRISO particles inside the fuel, and is therefore fully acceptable for a macroscopic description. In this first stage the temperature of the materials was yet not defined. Therefore, for the purposes of determining densities and dimensions, a room temperature of 293 K was assumed for all materials except for the heat pipes, which were considered to operate at 1100 K. Since the actual materials temperatures are not known a priori, a likely initial cross-section temperature of 1200 K is assumed. This value will be refined in subsequent iterative steps.

Quantities of interest within the core can be evaluated by applying tallies in the simulation. For the purposes of this work, the primary quantity of interest is the energy deposition rate. OpenMC offers various options to visualize the power distribution inside the core depending on the levels of accuracy and detail needed. This is done by spatial filters imposed on the tally. To better capture the core model and obtain high-quality score maps, an *ad hoc* unstructured mesh was created. A hexahedral mesh consisting of 198,000 elements was defined and applied to the model using the Virtual Toolkit (VTK) file format. A sketch of both cross section and axial discretizations is shown in Figure 2. This choice guarantees that the cell volumes are not excessively small, providing sufficiently good statistical sampling for the tallies.

Simulation parameters are a critical aspect of any Monte Carlo code, as they affect the statistical accuracy of the results. The key parameter is the total number of particles simulated, so, based on this, the other three (i.e., active batches, inactive batches and particles simulated in each batch) are adjusted accordingly. Inactive batches are used to allow the fission site distribution to reach a satisfactory con-

vergence. To improve fission site uniformity, the initial source was defined over the whole core but limited to fuel regions. Convergence can also be enhanced by using a fission source file from a previous simulation.

3.2. Code coupling

The coupling between OpenMC and OpenFOAM is done using the MEDCoupling library [5] and its python API. This library, which is provided with the SALOME platform, has been developed with the goal of improving numerical code coupling procedures and offers several methods that can be used to manipulate and interpolate numerical fields. The med format is used as default format for the meshes generated with hexaBundleMesher, an in-house developed algorithm for the generation of hexahedral meshes. In the present case, this tool has been used to generate the discretization of the full core geometry. As depicted in Figure 1, the coupling methodology starts with the mesh generation for both OpenMC and OpenFOAM: the first is used as a base for data sampling while the latter is used as computational grid for the thermal analysis.

OpenMC can handle meshes, as input files to be used for the sampling steps, with two different external libraries, namely MOAB and libmesh. The first only accepts tetrahedral meshes, while the latter, through the VTK library, can handle a wider set of mesh elements, including hexahedrons. The latter strategy has been used, based on two main reasons: the mesh construction algorithm of hexaBundleMesher, which generates purely hexahedral meshes, and the will of using meshes with a contained number of elements, thus avoiding impairing the quality of the sampling carried out by OpenMC, due to low statistics collected in small mesh cells. The OpenMC mesh is converted from the .med format into the .vtu format and then, after code execution, the output thermal power distribution is mapped onto the original .med format. Since the domain discretizations of the mesh tally and of the mesh for the thermal analysis are different, an interpolation step is needed to use the OpenMC computed thermal source in OpenFOAM. The field to be transferred is the power density (or power per unit volume) and the interpolation step is handled by the MEDCoupling library. The MEDCoupling allows to set the nature of the field (either intensive or extensive) so the interpolation algorithm is performed accordingly to the field nature. In the present case the interpolation is of type POP0 (i.e., for two cell-wise discretizations) for an intensive field. The interpolated field is finally converted into the OpenFOAM file format. The whole set of operations is organized into python scripts.

3.3. Thermal analysis using OpenFOAM

Thermal analyses were conducted using OpenFOAM v13. Studies of temperature distribution are of relevant importance to assess material limits and choices, improve assembly configuration (i.e. heat pipes global disposition), and give feedback for neutronics calculations. The model used to perform the thermal analysis represents a full core of 55 FA, with components described in Section 2. Simulations in OpenFOAM have been conducted using the foamMultiRun multi region solver, with each group of elements (i.e., fuel, moderators) treated as a separate region coupled with the nearby regions. Each region is treated as solid. The composition of the materials for all the regions modeled is summarized in Table I. At the current stage of analysis, temperature dependence is considered for all thermophysical properties, with the exception of density. For domain with composite materials (i.e. TRISO fuel) equivalent properties have been evaluated. The fuel region (compact TRISO) is composed by a SiC matrix within which TRISO particles are dispersed, and properties' homogenization has been considered. Its equivalent thermal conductivity has been evaluated with the Chiew-Gland theoretical model [6], while for density and heat capacity, weighted properties have been evaluated using the packing fraction F as the weight parameter. Similarly, Wicks' density and heat capacity have weighted properties with respect to porosity, and thermal effective conductivity of the liquid saturated wick is evaluated according to [8] neglecting working fluid advective effect. The vapor channel region is modeled as solid, converting the heat transfer capability, made possible by the latent heat carried by the vapor mass flow, into an equiv-

Table I. Regions material List

Region	Material	Thermal and Transport Properties ref.
Fuel	Compact TRISO	[6] [7]
Moderators	Zr ₅ H ₈	[7]
Wrappers	SiC	[7]
Casings	Inconel718	[7]
Wicks	SS316 + Liquid Sodium	[7] [8]
Vapor Channels	Sodium Vapor	[7] [9]

Table II. Simulation set of parameters of Case 1 and Case 2

	Case 1 - low statistics	Case 2 - high statistics
Total Batches	120	70
Inactive Batches	20	5
Particles/Batch	100'000	10'000'000
Active Particles	10'000'000	650'000'000
Source*	File	Box

*Method to define the initial neutron distribution: "File" corresponds to a previously generated source file; "Box" corresponds to a uniformly distributed spatial source.

alent thermal conductivity using the Darcy's equation [9]. Density and heat capacity refer to those of sodium vapor at saturated conditions. Properties of stand alone materials used in equivalent properties correlations and for mono-material regions (i.e. wrappers, casing) refer to [7].

The thermal analysis is carried out considering an internal power generation in the compact TRISO region obtained by the power field calculated in OpenMC and interpolated using the coupling method presented in Section 3.2. Interfaces between regions are thermally coupled. All the core walls facing the external environment are instead considered adiabatic but the HP condenser walls, that are set with a fixed temperature, corresponding to the conversion system nominal working condition, of 1100 K.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Thermal source

The primary quantity of interest is the core power (i.e., 500 kW for the entire core), obtained from a fission tally sampled on the unstructured mesh described above. Two OpenMC simulations were performed on the exact same core model but using different sets of simulation parameters, as summarized in Table

Figure 3. Power Density Distribution for the Central Fuel Assembly in Case 1 (left) and Case 2 (right)

Table III. Minimum and maximum temperature values (Kelvin) in the fuel and moderator regions of assembly 0 and 59 for the three levels of mesh refinement using the Case 2 power field.

		Assembly 0			Assembly 59		
		L0	L1	L2	L0	L1	L2
Moderator	Min	1153.2	1152.8	1152.7	1110.4	1110.4	1110.3
	Max	1452.7	1452.7	1452.6	1176.3	1176.3	1176.3
Fuel	Min	1101.2	1101.2	1101.2	1100.2	1100.2	1100.2
	Max	1503.8	1503.9	1503.8	1182.4	1182.4	1182.4

II. The cases were chosen to be markedly different to evaluate variability in result quality and to test the method's robustness when applied with different statistics simulations, particularly for the subsequent analyses on the temperature field. To ensure source convergence, for Case 1 (low statistics) a fission site map from a previous simulation was recovered. On the other hand, for Case 2 (high statistics) it was not necessary because of the extremely high number of particles processed at each batch. The 'Active Particles' is the parameter to be considered to control the accuracy of the statistical result. An anticipation of the scale difference between the two cases can be deduced from the Active Particle ratio. Moving from Case 1 to Case 2 the number of histories increases by a factor 65 and since the standard deviation is inversely proportional to the square root of the number of histories, we expect an enhancement in the result quality by approximately a factor of 8. For completeness, the constant multiplication factors for Case 1 and Case 2 are, respectively, 0.82213 ± 33 pcm and 0.82170 ± 4 .

In Figure 3, the power density of the central FA, for the core central cross section, is shown. For Case 1 (on the left) the distribution is evidently affected by statistical noise and therefore a clean gradient is hardly seen. On the other hand, Case 2 (on the right) presents a smooth map of the tally, with a clear resolution of the density power gradient. To further investigate the impact of the used set of parameters, on the uncertainty of the two simulations, the number of mesh cells exhibiting a relative standard deviation below 5% was counted. In the low statistics case, only 1.4% of the mesh cells met this criteria. In Case 2, 96.9% of mesh cells fell within the specified accuracy threshold, with a maximum relative error of 24% occurring on the border region, where neutrons leakage reduces the scoring frequency.

4.2. Thermal field

A preliminary mesh investigation has been performed by simulating single assemblies, in particular the central and a periferical ones. Given the meshing strategy adopted in hexaBundleMesher, the refinement can be set by adjusting the amount of cells in three directions, namely axial, radial (from center of pins to bulk region) and azimuthal (on pin circumference). Three mesh refinements, labelled as L0, L1 and L2, have been tested, with an approximate 1.5x increase factor of mesh cells along each dimension between adjacent levels of refinement. The global amount of cells, accounting together the mesh cells of all the regions, for the three levels of refinement are 507360, 1757700, and 6664440 respectively. It is recalled that the OpenMC discretization of the mesh tally, for the single assembly, is much coarser and consists of 3600 cells. No mesh refinement of the OpenMC solution has been considered. The mesh convergence analysis has been performed considering the Case 2 power field and by monitoring the fuel and moderator minimum and maximum temperatures. The values obtained are shown in Table III. From this mesh investigation it is shown that the coarsest mesh can be used to build the full core discretization.

Downstream the mesh investigation, a full core model has been created using as building block the fuel assembly element with the L0 mesh refinement. The full core thermal analysis is performed using both power fields resulting from Case 1 and Case 2 simulations to quantify the effect of the OpenMC collected statistics on the evaluated temperature fields. The boundary conditions for this analysis are those presented in Section 3.3. In Figure 4 the power density distribution for the axial and radial middle

Figure 4. Case 2 axial and radial power density distribution.

Figure 5. Relative error on temperature delta, between solutions computed with Case 2 and Case 1 source fields on fuel cross sections. On the right a sketch of the cross section planes.

core cross section, referred to Case 2 power field, is shown. To evaluate differences on temperature distribution resulting from the Case 1 and Case 2 power fields, the relative error with respect to Case 2, considering the delta between temperature distributions of both cases and the reference one of the condenser at 1100 K, has been evaluated. Variations lay in the range of $[-6,6]\%$ and are shown in Figure 5. Major variations arise at the core border, where uncertainties related to the lower statistics are bigger. Moving toward the core center differences flatten.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper we presented a methodology we developed to realize a numerical code coupling, between the Monte Carlo `OpenMC` and the CFD `OpenFOAM` codes, to accurately evaluate the temperature distribution in a nuclear reactor core for space applications. The `MEDCoupling` library has been used to handle the data collection and distribution between the codes through python scripts and the med file format. The methodology was applied to study a preliminary core configuration proposed in the SELENE project [4]. A full core temperature field evaluation has been done using two types of input sources, i.e., thermal power distributions, obtained by `OpenMC` using both a low and a high accurate statistical sampling, in terms of number of simulated particles. In the comparison of the obtained re-

sults, the relative error on temperature delta between the two cases shows a variance that lays within [-6, 6]%. Major differences interest spots nearby the core border, but good variances characterize the majority of the fuel region suggesting that, for design investigations, a low statistical sampling can still be considered reliable, with a sensible speed up in the design analysis. Future developments of the coupling algorithm will consider a feedback from OpenFOAM to OpenMC to account for thermal expansion of the geometry, temperature effect on cross section evaluations, and to evaluate how uncertainties affects final results.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kendrick, William Reed and Forget, Benoit. "Simulating Hydrogen Diffusion in ZrH Moderator and its Impact on Coupled Neutronic-Thermal Simulation of a Heat Pipe Microreactor." *EPJ Web Conf*, **volume 302**, p. 05008 (2024). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202430205008>.
- [2] M. J. Jeong, J. Im, S. Lee, and H. K. Cho. "Validation of Multiphysics Simulation Using OpenFOAM-PRAGMA Coupled Code for Heat Pipe Cooled Microreactor Core With the KRUSTY Experiment." *International Journal of Energy Research*, **volume 2024**(1), p. 7728721 (2024). URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1155/2024/7728721>.
- [3] L. Loi, S. Riva, C. Introini, F. Giacobbo, X. Wang, and A. Cammi. "OFELIA: An OpenMC-FEniCSx coupling for neutronic calculation with temperature feedback." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 428**, p. 113480 (2024). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0029549324005806>.
- [4] F. Lodi, R. Pergreffi, M. L. Hab, K. Mastrovito, S. Mannucci, C. Carrelli, and R. D. Vià. "Core design activities in support of the Moon Energy System with Nuclear Power (SELENE) Project: design requirements and supporting analyses." In *PHYSOR 2026 - The International Conference on Physics of Reactors (Submitted)*. Torino, Italy (2026).
- [5] CEA/DEN, EDF R&D, and O. et al. "MEDCoupling Developers' Guide (Library documentation)." URL <https://docs.salome-platform.org/latest/dev/MEDCoupling/developer/index.html>.
- [6] W. Mouhao, B. Shanshan, Z. Bing, L. Zhenzhong, and C. Deqi. "Multi-scale heat conduction models with improved equivalent thermal conductivity of TRISO fuel particles for FCM fuel." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology* (2022). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S173857332200568X>.
- [7] M. L. Hab, S. Mannucci, and K. Mastrovito. "SELENE - Database of Materials Properties V0.1." Technical report, ENEA Technical Report (to be issued) (2025).
- [8] B. Zohuri. *Heat Pipe Applications in Fission Driven Nuclear Power Plants*. Springer, Albuquerque, New Messico, USA (2019).
- [9] P. J. Brennan and E. J. Krociczek. *Heat Pipe Design Handbook*. I. B&K ENGINEERING, Maryland, USA (1979).